

ISic1548

I.Sicily inscription 1548

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

quarry mark

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Himera

Place of origin (modern)

Imera

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285069

EDCS 41300021

PHI 175610

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. *Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo.*

Sikelika 6. Palermo. At 16

Marconi, P. 1930. *Himera - Lo scavo del Tempio della vittoria e del Temenos. Atti e Memorie della Società Magna Grecia.* 1930: 41-200. At 63

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1970. *Le iscrizioni.* In Adriani, A., Bonacasa, N., Di Stefano,

C.A., Joly, E., Manni Piraino, M.T., Schmiedt, G, Tusa Cutroni, A.(eds.), *Himera I. Campagne di scavo 1963-1965*. Rome. pp. 343-356. At 352 n.18

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